

Impact of MGNREGA on Rural Development: A Case Study of Krushna Prasad GP of Puri District

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ABSTRACT

Rural development is considered to be of noticeable importance in the country today than in the olden days in the process of the evolution of the nation. It is a strategy that tries to obtain an improved and productivity, higher socio-economic equality and ambition, and stability in social and economic development. In the sphere of rural development the role of MGNREGA scheme is immiscible. The case study gives us information about the impact and incidence of MGNREGA scheme in the socio economic life of the common mass in a coastal district of Odisha.

KEYWORDS: MGNREGA, Rural Development, Developmental Schemes, Social Equality, Checking Migration

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INTRODUCTION

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) is considered as a "Silver Bullet" for eradicating rural poverty and unemployment, by way of generating demand for productive labour force in villages. Rural poverty and unemployment in India have grown in an unprecedented manner during the last few decades. There is a growing incidence of illiteracy, blind faith, hungry people, malnourished children, anemic pregnant women, farmer suicides, starvation deaths, migration resulting from inadequate employment, poverty, and the failure of subsistence production during droughts. In order to make solution of these problems and to provide livelihood security to rural unemployed, Government of India (GOI) enacted the National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) in 2005. It is the biggest poverty alleviation programme in the world which is started with an initial outlay of Rs.

11,300 crore in year 2006-07 and now it is Rs.61,500 crore (2020-21). This Act is now called as Mahatma Gandhi NREGA. The Act provides a legal guarantee for 100 days of employment in every financial year to adult members of any rural household will to do public work related unskilled manual work at the statutory minimum wage. Thus it is a universal programme. This minimum wage varies from state to state, in some states it is Rs. 180 whereas in other it is Rs. 175 or Rs. 177. According to the Act the minimum wage cannot be less than Rs. 1670. The 100 days of work figure was estimated because the agricultural season is only supposed to last roughly around 250 days and unskilled workers have no alternative source of income in the remaining part of the year.

HISTORY OF MGNREGA

NREGA has come after almost 56 years of experience of other rural employment programmes, which include

both Centrally sponsored Schemes and those launched by State Govt. These comprise the National Rural Employment Programme (NREP) 1980-89; Rural Landless Employment Guarantee Programme (RLEGP) 1983-89; Jawahar Rojgar Yojana (JRY) 1989-1990; Employment Assurance Scheme (EAS) 1993-99; Jawahar Gram Samridhi Yojana (JGSY) 1992-2002; Sampoorna Grameen Rojgar Yojana

The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) was notified on 7 September, 2005, NREGA, is one of the flagship schemes of the Government of India that touches lives of the poor and promotes inclusive growth. The Act aims at enhancing livelihood security of households in rural areas of the country by providing at least one hundred days of guaranteed wage employment in a financial year to every household whose adult members volunteer to do unskilled manual work.

The Act came in to force on 2 February 2006 in Anantapur District of Andhra Pradesh and was implemented in a phased manner. In Phase-one, it was introduced in 200 most backward districts of the Country. In was implemented in an additional 130 districts in phase-two during 2007-2008. As per initial target, NREGA was to be expanded countrywide in five years. However, in order to bring the whole nation under its safety net, and keeping in view the demand, the scheme was extended to the remaining 247 rural districts of India from 1 April 2008 in Phase III.

Phase-wise Extension of the Scheme in India

PHASE	YEAR	DISTRICTS
I	Feb 2006	200
II	Apr 2007	130
III	Apr 2008	247

Source: Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India.

The National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) is the first ever Act in the world that guarantees wage employment on an unprecedented scale. The primary objective is strengthening natural resource management through works that address the causes of chronic poverty such as drought, deforestation and soil erosion and thereby encouraging sustainable development. Outcomes of the process include strengthening grassroots processes of democracy and infusing transparency and accountability in governance. On 2 October 2009, the scheme was named as Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGS.).

Review of Related Literature

Since the date of implementation of NREGS various social scientists have made attempt to study the impact of NREGS and also its implementation procedures.

Khan, Ullah and Salluja (2007) have discussed the direct and the indirect effects of NREGP on employment generation and poverty reduction in a local area. For

this a detailed survey was done in a poor agricultural village with 400 households, nearly 2500 people. The survey recorded income and expenditure levels by type of household including large, small and marginal farmers, agricultural labour etc. The survey also recorded production activities undertaken by the inhabitants. This village study reveals that most people do not access the scheme, as they have not heard of the programme. They would like a more proactive role of the panchayat in deciding the infrastructure to be constructed. Almost everyone wants more work from the scheme and better facilities at the work place, There is enough evidence of fudging and mismanagement of records.

Dreze (2007) looks at the corruption in rural employment programs in Orissa and how this has continued in a NREGS as well. However, he believes that there is tremendous potential of NREGA in the survey areas, Where work was available, it was generally found that workers earned close to (and sometimes more than) the statutory minimum wage of Rs. 70 per day, and that wages were paid within 15 days or so. This is an unprecedented opportunity for the rural poor, and there was evident appreciation of it among casual labourers and other disadvantaged sections of the population. There is the hope among workers that NREGA would enable them to avoid long- distance seasonal migration. Further, there is plenty of scope for productive NREGA works in this area, whether it is in the field of water conservation, rural connectivity, regeneration of forest land, or improvement of private agricultural land.

Nayak, Behera, and Mishra (2008) conducted their study in 2 districts of Orissa mainly Mayurbhanj and Balasore. NREGA programme was first introduced in 200 most backward districts of the country. During the first phase itself. Mayurbhanj was selected along with other 18 backward districts of the state including KBK districts. The next phase, five more districts of Orissa were included under the scheme including Balasore, Mayurbhanj completed 3 years of NREGA implementation while Balasore has completed two. Both the districts are reported to have achieved certain goals and failed in others. This study shows that the state as a whole as well as the two sample districts are well in certain physical and financial parameters like provision of employment to those who demand jobs and maintenance of wage and non-wage ratio. However their performance in certain other important parameters like utilization of funds and creation of demand for jobs is not very encouraging. While the target is to guarantee 100 days of employment to each household, not many households have achieved this target. According to this report well thought out effort is necessary to address problems of NREGA in the state.

Institute of Applied Manpower Research, Delhi (2009), "All India Report on Evaluation of NREGA, a

Survey of Twenty Districts”, This study is based on evaluation of the NREGS which assess its impact by taking 20 districts from Northern, Western, Southern and North-east region of India and 300 beneficiaries from each districts. This study reveals that in many districts, affixing of photograph on job cards is not followed and in some places the beneficiary paid money for getting it. Job card was not designed to have sufficient space for all the entries in detail. Many household did not get the work within the stipulated 15 days time of demand for work, neither were they paid any unemployment allowance. On the utility of maximum number of days of works, only small fractions of households could utilize more than 35 days of work, remaining still lagging behind. The reason for non-utilization of maximum permissible 100 days of work is late starting of the scheme. In most of the worksites, excepting crèche, other facilities like shed, drinking water were provided. Due to the income generation through this scheme, the numbers of beneficiaries at the low earning level are reduced to nearly half in size. There is a rise of families who are spending more on food and non-food items.

Indian Institute of Technology, Madras, Chennai (2009): “ Evaluation of National Rural Employment Guarantee Act: In Districts: Cuddalore, Dindugal, Kanchipuram, Nagal, Thiruvallar, State: Tamilnadu”:- This study generally reveals the impact of MNRREGA in the state of Tamilnadu by taking 5 districts into account. In each districts 4 GPs were chosen.

This study shows many positive aspects of the programme. These are mainly:

- Villagers consider NREGA is promising to be a boon for improving rural livelihood.
- Provision of job within the village is very much encouraging to villagers.
- NREGA also ensured gender equality in rural Tamilnadu.
- The programme employed a very good proportion of scheduled caste and backward caste people.
- Involvement of SHG members improves people’s NREGS awareness and this is very important for future NREGS planning.
- Financial inclusion strategies like bank account opening and rural ATM for NREGS beneficiaries at four villagers of cuddalore block has resulted in multiplier effects of savings, financial safety etc.
- Registration are open throughout the year
- Most of the respondents perceived that payment were received within a week.

Dey, and bedi (2010) studied the functioning of the NREGS between Feb 2006 and July 2009 in Birubham District, west Bengal. Their study reveals that in order

to serve as an effective “employer of last resort”, the programme should provide more job days during lean season and wages should be paid in a timely manner. This study shows that in Birubham, there is universal awareness about the NREGS, job card have been made available to all those who have applied and NREGS related information is well maintained and relatively accessible. But there are long delays in wage payments during the first year of the programme, since then, the payment lag has declined and it is now in the range of 20 days.

Mathur (2009) states that in social audit undertaken in Andhra Pradesh, it was found that in certain villages, some people stated that they had not been paid for the work done. When comparisons were made of the payments as per the pass-book with the payments as per the job card, it was discovered that the job card did not contain the inner pages that record the work done by each person: the job card itself was incomplete. Earlier, several officials, field and Technical Assistants and Mates admitted to irregularities and about Rs.50,000 were returned.

Statement of the problem

The literature review carried out above reflects that though some researchers have done study on MGNREGS most of those are confined to economic aspect only. It is not comprehensive. Very few people have emphasized on implementation aspects of NREGS. Social aspects are not much highlighted. The present study will discuss both implementation and the impact of NREGS in a dominated village of PURI district, Odisha. While studying the study will emphasis on following questions.

1. What extent MGNREGA has helped in sustaining the rural livelihood?
2. Does MGNREGA become successful in improving the living condition of the poor?
3. Does it promise job to the needy?
4. Does it successful in reducing migration?
5. Is it really a livelihood generating programme than wage-earning scheme?
6. Are the people really aware about MGNREGA work?
7. Is the Act properly implemented as per its rules?

Research Gap:

Various articles have been published which show the cross countries and states comparison regarding the adoption of MGNREGA which generally focuses on the access to sustaining the rural livelihoods, creating productive assets, protecting the environment, reducing migration Fostering Social Equity. But the research gap which can be found is:

- No extensive study has been made regarding the understanding the implementation procedure of MGNREGA in Puri District of Odisha.
- Lack of Awareness mismanagement of job cards, poor Quality of works poor planning and lack of

coordination Among villagers and official member are measure problems of to implementation to MGNREGA in Puri District of Odisha.

Objective of the study

The main objectives of the present study are:

- Understanding the implementation procedure of MGNREGA in the study village of Puri district of Odisha.
- Understanding the impact of MGNREGA on rural livelihoods. In Puri district of Odisha.
- Empowering rural women and the poor through the provision of a right based law.
- Reducing migration the implementation of MGNREGA in Puri district of Odisha.
- To study the role of Fostering social equity, protecting the environment and creating productive assets in Puri district of Odisha.

Conceptual Framework:

While doing study it will reflect upon the various aspects of MGNREGA. It will develop a link among various factors like peoples' need, social and economic aspects. The concepts which are used in study are defined below as per the NREGA operational guidelines.

- **"Adult"** means a person who has completed his eighteenth years of age.
- **"Applicant"** means the head of a household or any of its other adult members who has applied for employment under the scheme.
- **"Household"** means the member of a family related to each other by blood, marriage or adoption and normally residing together and sharing meals or holding a common ration card.
- **"Minimum Wage"**, in relation to any area, means the minimum wage fixed by the State Govt. under Section 3 of the minimum wages Act, 1948 for agricultural labourers as applicable in that area.
- **"Unskilled manual work"** means any physical work which any adult person is capable of doing without any skill or special training.

Hypotheses:

In the study, the appropriate hypotheses that can be made are:

There is no financial and physical progress made by MGNREGA in MGNREGA is not effective in achieving rural livelihoods, reducing migration and empowering rural women in Puri district of Odisha.

- The role of fostering social equity and creating productivity assets are not satisfactory
- There are no significant changes made by MGNREGA in addressing unemployment and economic in security in rural areas.

Research Questions

1. MGNREGA enhances food security
2. MGNREGA provided some protection against extreme poverty

3. MGNREGA helped to reduce the distress migration
4. MGNREGA helped to reduce indebtedness
5. MGNREGA gave greater economic independence to women
6. MGNREGA generated better purchasing power in the local economy
7. MGNREGA has increased the local wage rate
8. MGNREGA has improved the scope of the children to go to school
9. The quality of MGNREGA work is satisfactory
10. Zero corruption exists in MGNREGA work
11. Improvement in roads and communication due to MGNREGA
12. Work MGNREGA work has improved the water level

Research Methodology:

Methodology

Universe

The Puri district is the universe for the proposed study

Census

The Krussnaprasad block of Puri district is the census for the proposed study

Sample and Sampling

Out of 21 GPs of Krussnaprasad block, 1 GP, i.e. Krussnaprasad has purposefully taken as sample (using purposive sampling) for evaluating the impact of MGNREGA.

Data Collection And Analysis

Data was collected both from primary and secondary sources, Primary data was collected from all the stakeholders of MGNREGA. Questionnaire surveys with the different stakeholders engaged in MGNREGA in the study site were organized. Semi structured informal interviews also taken from selected households. Transect walk into the MGNREGS worksites were conducted to have firsthand experience on the MGNREGS works at the community level. For gathering quantitative data household survey was conducted using the pre-tested schedules. Audio-video accessories were also used for collecting data. The secondary data was collected from official records, policy documents, published reports of similar projects, journals and literature from social science discipline.

Tools For Data Analysis

Simple statistical tools like average, percentage, etc will be used to analyse the data collected and diagrams like Pie-chart, Bar-Diagram will be used to present the analysis in graphical/ photo pictorial forms.

Socio Economic Profile of Puri District

1. Location:

Puri district is one of the centrally located districts in Odisha. It lies between 85° 9' to 86° 25' East longitude and between 19° 28' to 20° 10' North latitude. It is bounded by the Khordha district in north, Bay of Bengal in south, Jagatsinghpur district in the east and Ganjam district in the west.

2. Climate:

The climate condition of the district is generally hot with high humidity during April and May and cold during December to January. The monsoon generally breaks during the month of June, Annual rainfall of the district was 1936.0 m.m. in 2018 which is higher than the normal rainfall (1408.8 m.m.).

3. Area and Population:

The district has an area of 3479 sq.Kms. and 16.99 lakhs of population as per 2011 census. The district accounts for 2.23 percent of the states territory and shares 4.05 percent of the state's population. The density of population of the district is 488 per sq. Kms.. as against 270 person per sq.km of the state. It has 1707 villages (including 107 un-inhabited villages) covering 11 blocks, 11 Tahasils and 1 Subdivisions. As per 2011 census the schedule caste population is 325133 (19.1 %) and schedule tribe population 6129 (0.04 %). The literacy percentage of the district covers 84.7 against 72.9 of the state.

4. Agriculture:

During the year 2017-18, the net area sown was 100 thousand hectares against 3863 thousand hectares of the state. The production of paddy was 2600951 quintals, 93349 quintals mung, 22797 quintals biri, 537 quintals kulthi, and 12 quintals till, 10068 quintals groundnuts and 4781 quintal potato. During 2017-18, the total fertilizers used in Puri district is about 17079 MT with a breakage of 9882 MT nitrogenous, 3854 MT phosphatic and 3343 MT pottasic and the consumption of fertilizer per hectare is 88 Kg.

5. Irrigation:

During the year 2017-18, it is reported by Deputy Director Agriculture that the irrigation potential created during Kharif and Rabi are 103723 hectares and 66691 hectares respectively through all sources including major / medium irrigation projects in the district.

6. Co-operation:

The district has 208 agricultural Co-operative societies with a membership of 144249. The loan advances is to the tune of Rs. 25754.03 lakh and loan outstanding stood at Rs. 22124.91 lakhs as of 2017-18. The agricultural credit Co-operative societies as more or less evenly distributed across the 11 Blocks of the district.

7. Forest:

District of Puri has abundant of Forest area that contributed 3.94 % of the total geographical area of the district.

8. Veterinary Services:

During 2017-18, Milk production is 145.70 thousand MT, production of eggs is 139.14 lakhs nos. and production of meat is 9.29 thousand MT in this district. During 2017-18, 15 nos. of Hospitals and Dispensaries, 147 nos. of Livestock Aid centers and 127 Artificial Insemination Centers were functioning in the district.

9. Industry and Mining:

During the year 2017-18, 1515 nos. of micro small and medium enterprises have established with total capital investment of about Rs. 6763.20 lakhs with 4349 nos. of Employment generated in Puri district.

10. Power:

During the year 2017-18, villages so far electrified as on 31.03.2018 is 1576 which constitutes 98.5% to the total villages of the district.

11. Transport & Communication:

During 2017-18, 140.37 Kms. of National Highways, 43.56 kms of state highways, 24.99 kms. of Major district road, 335.76 kms of other district roads, 2037.78 kms of Inter-village road, 1923.11 kms of Intra-village road, 1694.93 Kms of village roads and 15.62 kms of forest roads are operating in the district.

12. Education:

There were 1294 nos. of primary schools, 753 nos. of Up-primary schools, 362 nos. of Secondary schools and 55 nos. of general colleges in the district during 2017-18. The teacher pupil ratio in the primary, upper primary, Secondary School stood at 22, 35 and 27 respectively.

13. Health:

The medical facilities are provided by different agencies like Govt., Private individuals and voluntary organizations in the district. There were 1 nos. DHH, 17 nos. CHC, 48 nos. PHC of the Allopathic medical institutions including 241 nos. of Sub Centre in the district during the year 2017-18. There were 16 nos. of Homoeopathic dispensaries and 1 no. Medical College Hospital & 24 nos. of Ayurvedic dispensaries in the district during the year 2017-18.

14. Banking:

As on December, 2018, there were 213 nos. of All Banks having 8633.37 crore rupees deposit and 3050.15 crore rupees credit in the district. The district has banking branches network of 213 out of which 49 (23.00%) were in the urban area, 27(12.68%) in semi-urban area and 137 (64.32%) in rural areas. The total number of ATMs in the district stood at 274

15. Collection of Land Revenue:

The total collection of land revenue in the district for 2017- 18 was Rs. 210.33 lakh.

16. Poverty Alleviation Programme:

In the district total no. of Job card issued was 2.29 Lakh and total no. of person days generated was 15.61 lakh during the year 2017-18.

17. Disaster Scenario:

In terms of Disaster activity the district is graded as very high risk zone for wind & cyclone, liable to get flooded and protected area for flood, moderate risk zone for drought, moderate damage zone for earthquake & major accident prone area for accident.

ADMINISTRATIVE MAP OF PURI DISTRICT

Analysis of the Progress Made Through MGNREGA

The following table gives us information about the category of works done under MGNREGA in the Krushnaprasad Block of Puri District during last 3 financial years

Name of the work	Numbers
Anganwadi	52
BNRGSK	2
Drought Proofing	169
Development of Fishery Unit	19
Development of Agricultural Field	46
Micro Irrigation Work	12
Play Ground	8
Renovation of Traditional Water Bodies	64
Rural Sanitation	2
Water Conservation and Harvesting	42
Rural Connectivity	99

The data represented in the above table can better be represented through the following bar-diagram.

Fund Allocation

The following table gives us information about the fund allocation for the scheme during the financial years, 2015-16 to 2020-21.

Financial Year	Amount spent in MGNREGA(In Lakh)
2015-16	110.57
2016-17	443.03
2017-18	451.81
2018-19	407.39
2019-20	463.9
2020-21	922.78

The above data can be represented through the following column.

Result of Interaction With Interview Schedule & Objective Generalization

The villagers are very much satisfied with the works done under MGNREGA, but due to using of machines instead manual labour, they are suffered. Excavation/creation of tank, construction of field channel & dug well has developed their agricultural practices manifold. Drought proofing has benefited them a lot as they are frequently affecting by drought. As per our objectives, the following conclusions were made:-

Implementation Procedure

Activities covered under MGNREGA

Permissible activities as stipulated in Para 1 of Schedule-I of Mahatma Gandhi NREGA are as under:

- Union Rural Development Ministry has notified works under MGNREGA, majority of which are related to agricultural and allied activities, besides the works that will facilitate rural sanitation projects in a major way.
- The works have been divided into 10 broad categories like Watershed, Irrigation and Flood management works, Agricultural and Livestock related works, Fisheries and works in coastal areas and the Rural Drinking water and Sanitation related works.
- Briefing the MGNREGA 2.0 (the second generation reforms for the rural job scheme) the priority of the works will be decided by the Gram Panchayats

in meetings of the Gram Sabhas and the Ward Sabhas.

- The Rural development also informed that the 30 new works being added in the Schedule 1 will also help the
- Rural sanitation projects, as for the first time toilet building, soak pits and solid and liquid waste management have been included under MGNREGA. Though the overall 60:40 ratio of labour and material component will be maintained at the Gram Panchayat level but there will be some flexibility in the ratio for certain works based on the practical requirements.
- Construction of AWC building has been included as an approved activity under the MGNREG Act. 'Guidelines for construction of Anganwadi Centres' under MGNREGS have been issued jointly by Secretary, WCD and Secretary, Ministry of Rural Development, on 13th August, 2015. Under MGNREGS, expenditure up to Rs.5 lakh per AWC building for construction will be allowed. Expenditure beyond Rs. 5 lakh per AWC including finishing, flooring, painting, plumbing, electrification, wood work, etc. will be met from the ICDS funds.

Impact on Livelihood

There was no discrimination of caste and tribes and genders in the implementation of the scheme. The

average man-days of employment per year were increased by 34.5% after joining MGNREGS (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme), average number of labour force per family increased by 15%. The average annual income of the respondents was increased to about 24% after joining the scheme, average annual consumption expenditure were also found to increase by about 14%, but there was no significant change in savings due to MGNREGS. The factors responsible for increase in income were found to be non farm income followed by total consumption expenditure, farm income, and expenditure on FPS (Fair Price Shop) as percent to total income, Expenditure on FPS as percentage to total expenditure, total savings and total man-days under MGNREGS. Inadequate works, political interference, lack of proper knowledge, lack of unity among the villagers for grievance redresses, lack of transparency in the local implementing agency, delayed wage payment, inconvenient mode of payment, inadequate worksite facilities especially first aids and undue wage cuts were some of the major problems faced by the sample respondents. Hardships faced by the local implementing agencies were low competence of Panchayat personnel, weak convergence of MGNREGS with other developmental departments that has led to inadequate technical support from concerned departments, delay in payment to beneficiaries due to delay in writing the Measurement Book by the concerned Engineers from block office, interest shown by beneficiaries only in attending to the works undertaken for wage, but not in performing the work satisfactorily, internet problems also hinder the work of updating MIS (Management Information System) in Gram Panchayats.

Women Empowerment

Women's participation in the scheme has enabled them to come out of their homes not only for the purpose of work but to visit panchayat offices and banks, which was absent in the earlier days. This has elevated the women in the society to a higher status of becoming income earning workers. Though there is absence of ample amount of studies on the issues of change in gender roles of the women employed on MGNREGS sites yet researches have noted on the increased confidence among women. Women remains confined to the household chores, occupation and in the formulation of social safeguard policy. There is a refusal to accept the dual role of women in the as care givers and income earners in the family as a collective concern of the state. Since women remain as caregivers of the family, their comfort zone of work area is near their home with flexible timings etc. all of which are fulfilled by the MGNREGS. The central governments have taken more initiative, but still there are lot of issues and challenges there in working place among women who take part in the scheme. The government should create more awareness programme for rural

women so that they could know the important provisions made for them in MGNREGA and payments be made through bank accounts only and on time in particular. It is evidenced from the literature review the research implications for the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme will definitely help policy makers, government, panchayats, rural women, and human resource practitioners to provide suitable suggestions and help practitioners and both the state and central government to look at the existing solutions for the problems in domain and adopt the methodologies for new sectors such as MGNREGA.

Reducing Migration

One of the major problems that MGNREGA addresses is that of distress migration. The distress migration is of grave concern which is adopted as a survival strategy on account of push factors and cannot be seen as indicative of development. Mobility under these circumstances is a compulsion not on account of a rational choice but rather due to lack of choice. The MGNREGA is providing alternative survival opportunity in the place of origin and the necessary precondition for a rational choice decision. The distress migration has serious adverse social implications often contributing to precarious employment conditions, low wages, insecurity of incomes and other forms of exploitation seen as propelling un-freedom for the laboring poor. Since the migrants from the study village end up in construction activity, brick kilns and stone work all of which are known to have precarious conditions and un-free employment relations. We observe that while MGNREGA has played a significant role in reducing the distress, the program is yet to realize its full potential. While some problems are linked with the development of infrastructure such as post offices etc., that would improve the access to the beneficiary households, other problems are linked to functional gaps such as lack of proper information dissemination. A third category of problems are linked with inadequacy of resources and proper designing of the activities to create durable, productive public assets. The more substantive challenges in this context are to do with the structural revival of the rural economy making it part of the priority areas as part of the development model and addressing the political economy questions of enable collective action seeking to democratize power relations in the rural societies which is the only method to control pilferages and other distortions intruding and constraining the exercise of the right guaranteed to the people.

Fostering Social Equality

The MGNREGA programme has achieved many social and economic achievements which are being reported by various research scholars and government institutions (MGNREGA Sameeksha, 2012) Provided guaranteed wage employment of 100 days in a financial year, thus enhanced social security and living

standards. It has provided around Rs. 1,10,700 crore as worker wages from FY 2006 up to FY 2011–12. It reveals a positive impact of this transfer on household income, monthly per capita expenditure, food security and health of the beneficiaries. In Chhattisgarh, Orissa, Jharkhand and Andhra Pradesh, income of rural labour households has gone up as a result of this programme. Provided work opportunities for women by reserving 1/3 of employment, which enabled women empowerment in rural areas. Various research reveals that this programme has led to an increase in agriculture wage rates and boosts the real daily agricultural wage rates by 5.3 per cent. The wage effect is equal for both men and women and is in favour of unskilled labour. Social audit increases transparency and trust among rural communities. Prevented seasonal or distressed migration towards cities and given work opportunity at native place and increased household income which is used for food security, education of dependents, health care and debt repayments. In some cases, earnings were utilized to acquire durable assets and created amenities in households. Various studies revealed that MGNREGA has succeeded in high participation from marginalised groups including the SCs and STs. At the national level, the share of SCs and STs in the work provided under MGNREGA has been high at 40–50 per cent in each year. In FY 2011–12 alone, 40 per cent of the total person-days of employment (84 crore out of 209 crore) were provided to SCs and STs. The increase in employment and wages resulted in an increase in household income. In Chhattisgarh, the increase in household income ranged from 23–160 per cent (as compared to 2005–06), in Jharkhand it ranged from 60–70 per cent and in Odisha it ranged from 30–40 per cent (Banerjee and Saha, 2010). Build rural infrastructure thereby strengthening the village communities. A survey conducted across six states revealed that 82 per cent of the widows regarded MGNREGA as a very important source of income, and of the total sample, 69 per cent of the women accepted that it helped them avoid hunger. Different studies also observe that post MGNREGA, women have greater control over their wages and have been spending them on repaying small debts, paying for their children's schooling and bearing medical expenses, etc. Provided equal opportunity for all workers without any discrimination based on caste, religion or gender. This scheme enhanced mobility which comes with the higher status of being income-earning workers. Women managed their family relations in employment and in the formulation of social protection policy. This scheme also increases social skills like communication, mobility, participation, decision making among women beneficiaries. It enhanced financial inclusion of beneficiary to Indian economy as the wages given through bank accounts and post offices. In the study areas it also helps in fostering social equality. The workless laborers now get 100 days employments

guarantee, along with normal works like that of in agricultural fields and private works. We can say it becomes a panacea for all the problems of the rural stakeholders.

Significance of the Study

The present study attempts to understand the implementation procedures of MGNREGS and its impact on rural livelihoods in a dominated Panchayat of Puri district, Odisha. This project focuses on the role of GP to generate sufficient employment opportunities, the procedures for registration, issuance of job cards, and application for employment. This would enable us to understand and examine the institutional mechanisms under which the entire programme is being implemented. The problems and prospects of MGNREGA can then be better understood and accordingly, necessary measures can be devised to make the programme realize its set objectives. The outcome of the study will help in understanding the problem of implementation of the project. It will help in formulating the better policy and strategy for the future.

CONCLUSION

Thus, from the above discussion we can conclude that the government is now more serious about the poverty eradication from India. The government of India has also taken significant steps towards enhancing the participation of grass root bodies in the implementation of poverty alleviation programmes. The socio-economic programmes are now more targets oriented and putting direct assault on poverty. Programmes like MGNREGA should be given more weightage in the planning process; so that the poverty from villages can be reduced to great extent. The success and effectiveness of these programmes will depend upon the sustained, intelligent and enthusiastic involvement and cooperation of the village community. However the efforts of state as well as central governments cannot be ignored but despite of that there will always be a scope of improvement in every aspect of implementation process. Therefore, simultaneous focus on two major aspects is required. First, the delivery systems need streamlining so as to

make them more responsive to the people and motivate them with a missionary zeal. Second, the PRIs need to be more intimately involved in planning, implementation and monitoring of development programmes.

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